

RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant Program Tracking & Evaluation

2023
Mid-Year
Report

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Executive Summary

Background

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality¹. The Community Collaboration Grant (C2G) program awards up to \$50,000 to support community partners to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives for underserved populations, as defined by the NIH².

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC), comprehensively assesses the RADx-UP C2G program's productivity and impact by evaluating its projects.

Objectives

This mid-year evaluation report details the RADx-UP C2G's key evaluation findings that indicate RADx-UP C2G program outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impacts between December 6, 2022 through August 7, 2023. **Figure 1** summarizes the C2G evaluation aims.

This report also presents an opportunity for collaboration with RADx-UP, Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC), and NIH stakeholders to identify how to improve services delivered to the C2G awardees.

Figure 1. C2G Evaluation Aims

Methods

This mixed-method evaluation uses a longitudinal approach to collect data on project updates, activities, outcomes, and CDCC support and resources used by the awardees at a minimum of three time points. Data sources include C2G program records, project intake surveys, evaluation surveys, and a follow-up qualitative interview that takes place six months after the closeout of the program. The T&E team is responsible for distributing the surveys, analyzing the data, and communicating the results to C2G leadership and other stakeholders.

For the purpose of this report, only active cycles which include Cycle 4, Cycle 5, and Cycle 6, and project data that has been collected between December 6, 2022 through August 7, 2023 is included in the findings.

Results

Currently, there are 70 total C2G projects across 7 funding cycles. This section highlights commonly reported program activities, challenges and barriers faced by projects, utilization and impact of CDCC services, and impact of the C2G program on clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits.

Program Activities

COVID-19 training, education, development, and dissemination of COVID-19 testing communication materials are the most common project activities.

- Eighty seven percent of projects include an activity to provide training or education to their community around COVID-19 testing projects.
- Eighty four percent of projects are developing and disseminating COVID-19 testing communication materials.

Two-thirds of projects include COVID-19 testing as part of their project activities via on-site mobile and non-bile testing and at-home test kit distribution.

Challenges and Barriers

The most common ongoing challenges reported include **testing hesitancy and administrative challenges**. *Testing hesitancy* challenges are challenges related to unwillingness or inability to get tested in the target population and have been cited as ongoing challenges due to “COVID fatigue” among communities. *Administrative challenges* are defined as challenges in paperwork, processes, and procurement of non-testing materials.

CDCC Services: Utilization and Impact

Overall, projects reported satisfaction with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support. Satisfaction is measured in terms of helpfulness, effectively addressing feedback received from projects, the capacity to resolve project concerns, promptness and ease of accessing support. Between **74 percent and 84 percent of projects reported satisfaction with the support provided by the RADx-UP CDCC**.

The T&E team also sought to understand the quality of how the RADx-UP CDCC is fostering collaboration, inclusion, and project engagement within RADx-UP. This is assessed by measuring the quality of the CDCC's support in adapting activities to fit project needs, fostering data equity, practicing cultural competence and responsiveness, and engaging underserved populations and community partners in program planning, leadership and decision making. Between **81 percent and 90 percent of projects indicated Good or Very Good quality of CDCC support in these domains**.

Translational Science Benefits Outcomes

The Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) is a framework designed to support the assessment of clinical and translational research outcomes to measure clinical and community health impacts³. The T&E team uses the core components of the TSBM to evaluate the impact of the C2G program in demonstrating* **the clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits** of investing in increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities.

Clinical Benefits

Thirty-two percent of projects reported at least one project outcome in the Clinical Key Benefit Area. Clinical benefits include COVID-19 diagnostic procedures including **methods and techniques performed to diagnose COVID-19**.

Community and Public Health Benefits

One hundred percent of projects reported at least one project outcome in the Community & Public Health Key Benefit Area. Community and public health benefits include the implementation of **community health services, development and/or dissemination of health education resources, and increased testing delivery and uptake**.

*Benefits can be classified as demonstrated or potential. Demonstrated benefits are those that have been observed, and potential benefits are those that are expected but not yet demonstrated.

Economic Benefits

Forty one percent of projects reported at least one project outcome in the Community & Public Health Key Benefit Area. Economic benefits include **potential cost savings** by reduced financial costs of services or goods.

Policy Benefits

Five percent of projects reported at least one project outcome in the Policy Key Benefit Area. Policy benefits include the advocacy of certain **policies to address the COVID-19 pandemic**.

Recommendations and Next Steps

Based on the findings from this mid-year report, the T&E team has developed next steps and recommendations for improving the C2G program and reaching the evaluation goals.

- **Address challenges cited by projects**, as possible, focusing on the most cited challenges, testing hesitancy and administrative challenges.
- Maintaining **continuous feedback loops** between the UNC T&E team, the C2G Program Administration team, and C2G awardees. **Figure 2** illustrates how these feedback loops work amongst the teams- the T&E team reports findings to the C2G Program Administration team, and in turn the C2G Program Administration team communicates this to the EITs who then communicate with the C2G funded projects. Should any questions or concerns arise, the C2G funded projects will communicate back to the EITs.

As the C2G program comes to an end, the next steps for the Tracking & Evaluation team include:

- **Monitor program progress** through biannual evaluation surveys and reports will be completed every six months.
- Conduct Sustainability interviews (six months post-project) to **assess the longer-term impacts of the C2G program**, including any sustained project activities and other achievements that stemmed from the project (additional external funding, new partnerships, etc.).
- **Dissemination of qualitative Sustainability interview findings** among stakeholders.

Figure 2. C2G Program Feedback Loop

Project Characteristics

Currently, there are a total of 70 C2G projects across seven funding cycles. For the purpose of this report, only active cycles which include Cycle 4, Cycle 5, and Cycle 6, and project data that has been collected between December 6, 2022 through August 7, 2023 is included in the findings. C2G projects have a wide reach of underserved, and COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations. The most common underserved populations served by C2G projects include **socioeconomically disadvantaged populations, Hispanic/Latino, and Black/African American populations.**

Most (87.5%) C2G projects collaborate with community partner organizations to carry out their project. The T&E team tracks the number and type of project partners, with most common types of community partners being community centers.

Total Number of C2G Funded Projects to Date by Cycle, Active v Inactive (n= 70)

Underserved Populations Served by C2G Projects, (n= 32 projects)

C2G Project Partners (n= 28 projects)

Project Activities

The most common project activities include **training and education around COVID-19 testing topics and generating COVID-19 testing communication materials**. In addition to the activities listed in the 6- and 12-month survey, **two-thirds of projects engage their community COVID-19 testing** via on-site mobile and non-bile testing and at-home test kit distribution.

C2G Project Activities, n= 31

Did Your Project Engage the Community in COVID-19 Testing? (n= 24)

Type of COVID-19 Testing (n= 16)

*We met with executive directors and staff from organizations in an effort to **collaborate, train and educate on the importance of COVID testing in underserved communities**. We successfully completed 4 large community pop ups, 6 smaller pop ups during symposiums in rec centers, schools and libraries and we also were able to create a YouTube channel and reach hundreds. Our totals for training are over 60 individuals.*

C2G Cycle 4 Project, Community Center Organization

*We hosted 2 **live Q&A sessions on social media platforms** to answer questions regarding COVID-19 testing and vaccination updates. Our **sessions were hosted by our Community Health Coordinator** who is a registered nurse.*

C2G Cycle 5 Project, Community Center

***Community leaders conducted outreach** outside tiendas, supermarkets, laundromats, the Guatemalan Consulate, mobile home parks, and throughout community events and festivals. Through activities, we have **reached over 10,000 individuals**. This year alone, our community leaders have distributed 1,083 bags with material, 889 masks, 390 hand sanitizers, 2,546 testing kits, and reached a total of 1,443 individuals.*

C2G Cycle 4 Project, Community Center Organization

*Participants who complete **Community Drive-Up COVID-19 testing** receive educational information in the form of a **handout about PCR test results** and instructions on next steps. When test results return positive, participants are contacted via phone and given instructions on recommended quarantine and isolation periods, as well as home care to manage symptoms. In 2022, the organization **completed 6,799 PCR COVID-19 tests**.*

C2G Cycle 4 Project, Medical Care Organization

Challenges

Resolved and Ongoing Challenges Experienced by Projects (n= 7 projects)

Seven out of 22 projects reported on delays or roadblocks they have faced during their project period that have either been resolved or are still ongoing. The most common ongoing challenges reported include **testing hesitancy and administrative challenges**. *Testing hesitancy* challenges are challenges related to unwillingness or inability to get tested in the target population and have been cited as ongoing challenges due to “COVID fatigue” among communities. *Administrative challenges* are defined as challenges in paperwork, processes, and procurement of non-testing materials.

As challenges are observed, the T&E team is communicating these challenges to leadership so that they can be addressed in a timely manner.

Resolved roadblocks vary across projects. Some examples of resolved roadblocks that have been experienced by projects include adapting their project activities to fit the needs of the target population, collaborating with community partners to disseminate testing kits before they expired, and development of materials that inform community members of where to access free testing.

*In the beginning, there was some **resistance to the in-house barber facilities** and pricing. Through quick thinking and ingenuity, we morphed into a **mobile barber FRESH tour**, which gave us more flexibility to touch more individuals in environments we controlled.*

C2G Cycle 5 Project, Outreach Challenge Resolved

*...As our community emerges from the pandemic it is clear that organizers such as the city, county, and local non-profits are easing back into large scale community events. Several times we received notifications of rescheduling of large events. **This was a barrier because we counted on large events to distribute large quantities of testing kits that had expiration dates. We pivoted and leaned on our community partners to distribute testing kits.***

C2G Cycle 4 Project, Testing Site Challenge Resolved

*COVID Vaccine fatigue and **scarce free testing sites** was a roadblock that both **Asian and African/Caribbean communities in Philadelphia** have faced... To counter this, we have collaborated in a campaign that provides these communities testing sites based on **availability, language access, and cost**. This campaign highlights specific areas of Philadelphia for community members to access the nearest COVID testing clinic near them.*

C2G Cycle 6 Project, Testing Hesitancy & Structural Barriers Challenges Resolved

CDCC Services: Utilization and Impact

This section describes the findings from survey items assessing the utility and quality of support provided by the CDCC⁴.

Overall, projects reported satisfaction with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support. Satisfaction is measured in terms of helpfulness, effectively addressing feedback received from projects, the capacity to resolve project concerns, promptness and ease of accessing support. Between **74 percent and 84 percent of projects reported satisfaction with the support provided by the RADx-UP CDCC.**

Overall satisfaction with the support provided by the RADx-UP CDCC (n= 31)

The T&E team also sought to understand the quality of how the RADx-UP CDCC is fostering collaboration, inclusion, and project engagement within RADx-UP. This is assessed by measuring the quality of the CDCC's support in adapting activities to fit project needs, fostering data equity, practicing cultural competence and responsiveness, and engaging underserved populations and community partners in program planning, leadership and decision making. Between **81 percent and 90 percent of projects indicated Good or Very Good quality of CDCC support in these domains.**

Quality of how the RADx-UP CDCC is fostering collaboration, inclusion, and project engagement within RADx-UP (n= 31)

CDCC Services: Engagement Impact Teams (EITs)

The Engagement Impact Teams (EITs) work closely with the C2G projects to provide support during the project period. The T&E team assesses satisfaction with the EITs in the 6- and 12-month evaluation surveys. The majority of projects agree or strongly agree that the EIT's are timely in answering project questions, that the organizational model of accessing RADx-UP CDCC services through the EITs is effective, and that the EITs facilitate connections to RADx-UP CDCC services and resources relevant to project needs.

Satisfaction with support provided by the EITs is measured by assessing EIT cultural competency, responsiveness, onboarding and training resources, and knowledge in resolving project needs. Between **61 percent and 67 percent of projects are satisfied or very satisfied with the support provided by the EITs.**

It is worth noting that in both the 6- and 12-month surveys there is a section that asks projects to share the most helpful RADx-UP CDCC support services and of those that respond, many comment on the support of the EITs, especially the monthly meetings, noting the **value in the opportunity to provide updates, stay informed about resources and opportunities available to meet their needs, and stay on track with their progress.**

Satisfaction with EIT Support Services (n= 31)

Satisfaction with Support Provided by the EITs (n= 31)

RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant Program: A Summary of TSBM Outcomes

The Community Collaboration Grant Program (C2G) has funded 69 projects across 7 funding cycles.

Translational Science Benefits Model¹

IMPACT PROFILE

The Impact

The C2G funded projects resulted in clinical, community & public health, policy and economic benefits.

Through community health services, training, and education projects increased access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in communities of underserved and vulnerable populations.

The Challenge

Communities across the United States are disproportionately impacted by COVID-19, with many underserved and vulnerable communities' facing barriers to COVID-19 testing and diagnosis.

COVID-19 testing, isolation, contact tracing, among others, in communities will help decrease COVID-19 transmission and save lives.

The Approach

C2G provides Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) subawards aimed to increase the capacity for COVID-19 testing expertise within the community. Increasing training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, contact tracing, among others, in communities will increase our ability to decrease COVID-19 transmission and save lives.

The goal of the program is to improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations

The T&E team employs the core components of the Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model¹ to assess the translation of innovation related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit underserved communities at large.

Key Benefits

CLINICAL

COVID-19 Diagnostic procedures.

Testing diagnostic services performed for individuals in the community to diagnose COVID-19.

COMMUNITY

Community Health Services.

Community members and org's working together to provide COVID-19 services to the community to increase access to and uptake of COVID-19 testing.

COMMUNITY

Health Education Resources. Tailored resources that inform community members of COVID-19 benefits and risks through targeted delivery.

COMMUNITY

Testing Accessibility. Equity and ability for all to gain entry to and to receive COVID-19 testing services

ECONOMIC

Cost Savings. Reduced financial costs of COVID-19 testing services by providing free COVID-19 testing and distributing free at-home test kits and preventative supplies to communities.

The team

Tracking & Evaluation team: G, Dave Tara Carr, Shelly Maras, Valerie Lucas, Taylor Baldwin, Jade Hollars, Rossana Roberts

C2G Program Administration Team:

Find out more: <https://radx-up.org/grants/community-collaboration/>
<https://radx-up.org/about/coordination-center/tracking-evaluation-cdcc-radxup/>

RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant Program: A Summary of TSBM Outcomes

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Translational Science Benefits Model¹

IMPACT PROFILE

Key Benefits: An In-Depth Look

The figure below illustrates the TSBM Indicators¹ and the number of projects by cycle with which their outcomes correspond with.

Project Outcomes Mapped to TSBM Key Benefit Areas (n= 22 projects)

Increase capacity for COVID-19 rapid testing in the Knoxville community by 60 no-appointment tests each week.

Establish a call center and provide bilingual staff to attend all the calls and texts received by community members requesting information or appointments for COVID-19 testing or vaccines

Distribute safety kits including disinfectant wipes, gloves, masks, hand soap and hand sanitizer to over 500 hundred individuals and families.

Advocate in City Hall for a surge plan and the implementation of a wastewater track.

Hire and train staff to meet extended hours for COVID-19 testing site. (2 staff members worked extended hours to provide COVID-19 test, 7 individuals were trained to do COVID-19 testing at the Open Door free clinic).

Trained 13 Latinx community leaders, 10 youth fellows, and several staff members on COVID-19 outreach and education, and in the use of COVID-19 test kits.

References

1. About RADx-UP - RADx-UP. Accessed August 20, 2023. <https://radx-up.org/about/>
2. Community Collaboration Grant Program - RADx-UP. RADx-UP. Accessed August 24, 2023. <https://radx-up.org/grants/community-collaboration/>
3. Luke DA, Sarli CC, Suiter AM, et al. The Translational Science Benefits Model: A New Framework for Assessing the Health and Societal Benefits of Clinical and Translational Sciences. *Clin Transl Sci*. 2018;11:77-84. doi:10.1111/cts.12495
4. RADx-UP Coordination Center - RADx-UP. Accessed August 24, 2023. <https://radx-up.org/about/coordination-center/>